

Ornithological observation

I. Scenario Description

A collaborative app supports the sharing of audiovisual resources related to bird-watching experiences within a global geographic space represented on an interactive map. Users of the system, referred to as observers, remain interconnected and can manage locations, photos, videos, audio recordings, bird characteristics, and personal notes.

Scenario 1:

- R1: When an observer is exploring an area in search of birds, their geolocation is shared and displayed on the global map using a live marker.
- R2: The map also visualizes, through icons, the bird sightings reported by all observers in the past 8 hours.
- R3: The sightings closest to the observer within the last 2 hours are collected in real time in a list, with those involving rare species (e.g., osprey) highlighted.

Scenario 2:

- R4.1: When an observer records a sighting but is not fully certain of the species, he/she can request verification from other observers.
- R4.2: These observers must respond to the unconfirmed species sighting request (including location, photo/video, suggested species, description, etc.) with either a positive or negative verification. If two observers respond positively, the sighting is confirmed and added to the map. The system will use sound notifications and visual signals on the map to represent the query and responses (positive = green; negative = red; confirmation = blue), in order to enhance user awareness of the verification process.

II. Awareness Description Diagrams

